

A STUDY ON RURAL MARKETING OF FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS [MILK] PRODUCTS IN GUNTUR DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract:

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) also known as consumer-packaged goods are consumed every day by the average consumers and it has become part of everyday life for most of the urban and rural people, used up over short period of days, weeks or months and within one year. The items in FMCG include all consumables (other than groceries, pulses) and non-consumable that people buy at regular intervals. Since the past few years, the income of rural Indians is raising and their mindset to buy FMCG products are increasing rapidly with improving their lifestyle. With this improving interest of rural consumers over FMCG products, the study entitled " Study on Rural Marketing of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) Milk was undertaken to investigate the buying pattern of rural consumers in Vinukonda mandal of Guntur district, the factors affecting the buying pattern of rural consumers, the factors affecting the buying behavior of rural consumers, their level of satisfaction towards the changing the attributes like Price, Quality, Availabilities, offers, and purchasing experience and the various opportunities and challenges for FMCG companies in rural areas. The products chosen for this case study are milk and its importance. This study also reveals that how a rural consumer makes the decision to spend their available resources (time, effort, money) on consuming related items and their satisfaction levels towards their FMCG product available in their locations. The study also identifies how their power of buying the FMCG products is utilized from different stores. It also revealed the affective of various sources of information affecting the buying behavior of FMCG brands and also the loyalty of rural consumers on sticking to the same brand.

Key word :- Marketing, Economic, production, rural consumers

Introduction:

Indian rural market with its colossal size and demand base offers great opportunities to marketers. Two thirds of India's consumers live in rural areas where almost one third of the national income is generated. It is seen as a profusion of opportunities, whether for marketing durables, textiles and garments, personal care products or financial services. A rural marketer is faced with an entirely different set of conditions and problems while marketing in the rural area as compared with an urban area. For most marketers planning to enter the rural markets, distribution poses a serious challenge. For the successful exploration of rural markets, a basic requirement is infrastructure. The absence of such an infrastructure is aggravating the distribution challenges in rural India. There are many other challenges that FMCGs companies face in tackling rural markets, viz., geographically scattered nature of rural markets, their small size, remoteness, poor connectivity and tremendous heterogeneity. Low level of literacy, too many languages and dialects, cultural diversities, inadequate banking facilities, spurious products, low per capita disposable incomes, acute dependence on the monsoon seasonal demand, and media darkness are some other serious limitations. Therefore, the real problem for the marketers to penetrate into rural markets lies in understanding the heterogeneous rural consumers, reaching products to these remote locations, and communicating.

Milk is a nutrient-rich liquid food produced by the mammary glands of mammals. It is the primary source of nutrition for young mammals (including breastfed human infants) before they are able to digest solid food. Early-lactation milk, which is called colostrum, contains antibodies that strengthen the immune system and thus reduces the risk of many diseases. Milk contains many other nutrients, including protein and lactose. While Humans are the primary consumers of other mammal's milk, other interspecies consumption of milk has been observed.

Research methodology:**Selection of district:**

Among all 26 districts of Andhra Pradesh, Guntur district was selected purposely for the present study because the district has large number of consumer of milk in study area.

Selection of block:

A list of blocks taken from District Headquarters of Andhra Pradesh Visakhapatnam. In the Guntur district have total 57 blocks. Out of these blocks, Vinukonda was selected purposely for the study.

Selection of villages:

There are 21 villages in Vinukonda block. 5percentvillages were selected randomly in Vinukonda block.

Sl.No.	Name of Village	Respondents
1.	Andugulapadu	19
2.	Brahmanapalle	24
3.	Chowtapalem	14
4.	Dondapadu	27
5.	Naragayapalem	16

Selection of respondents:

10percent respondents were selected randomly on the basis of location and respondents of total 8 Villages nearby of Vinukonda block.

S.No.	Block Name of village	No. of Respondents					Total
		Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	Medium	Large	
1.	Andugulapadu	1	2	4	5	6	18
2.	Brahmanapalle	1	2	3	4	4	14
3.	Chowtapalem	2	3	2	3	1	11
4.	Dondapadu	2	4	2	3	6	17
5.	Naragayapalem	3	1	2	1	1	8
		9	12	13	16	18	100

Data Collection:**Method of Primary Data Collection:**

The primary data was collected from consumers, merchants and different agencies through personal interview.

Method of Secondary data collection:

The secondary data was collected from the office of the agricultural department, and different organization websites also helpful.

Analytical Tools:

Chi square

A chi-square statistic tool is one way to show a relationship between two categorical variables. The chi-squared statistic is a single number that tells you how much difference exists between your observed counts and the counts you would expect if there were no relationship at all in the population. It is used for data that consist of variables distributed across various categories and is denoted by χ^2 . This formula will be use for identifying the demographic pattern of the consumers. The chi-square formula is:

$$\chi^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2/E_i$$

where,

O_i = observed value (actual value)

E_i = expected value.

Marketing Margin:

The term marketing margin refers to the different in places for a commodity at different stages of the marketing system. In the widest sense marketing margin is the difference in price received by the producer and the price paid by ultimate consumer. Marketing margin include all costs of assembling processing storage transportation, handling, wholesaling and retailing in the process of marketing moving of produce from the farmer to the ultimate consumer.

Marketing Margin = Retail or Selling price- Actual cost

Price Spread

Results And Discussion:

To find out marketing channels, market share, marketing efficiency and marketing cost

The price spread is workout by computing the difference between the market price and the net price received by the producers. This difference represents the gross marketing margin.

$$GMM = P_c - P_{fb}$$

Where,

GMM = Gross Marketing Margin

P_c = Price Paid by consumer

P_{fb} = Price received by producer

Cost of marketing

The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity till it reaches the ultimate consumer was computed as follow.

$$C = C_f + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Where.

C= Total cost of marketing

C_f= Cost borne by the producer farmer from the produce leaves the farm till the sale of the produce, and

C_{mn}= Cost incurred by the middlemen in the process of buying and selling

Marketing Efficiency

Marketing efficiency is the degree of market performance. It is the ratio of market output to market input

Conventional Method

$$\text{Index of marketing efficiency (E)} = O / I * 100$$

Where,

O= value added by the marketing system

I= cost of market intermediaries

Channel-I:

TABLE 1: Price Spread of Milk In Channel I

S. No	Particulars	Price/Ltr.
1	Net price received by producer	50
2	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Consumer	50

Table 1 reveals the data about the how much net price received by producer and also sale price of producer

Channel-II:

TABLE 2: Price Spread of Milk In Channel II

S. No	Particulars	Price/Ltr.
1	Net price received by producer	45
2	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Milkmen	45
Cost incurred by the Milkmen		
3	Transportation and other costs incurred	5
4	Margin of Retailer	5
	Sale price of Milkman/ Purchase price of consumer	55
	Total Marketing cost	5
	Net margin	5
	Price Spread	10
	Marketing Efficiency	2

Table 2 reveals the net price, sale price transportation costs net margin price spread in marketing efficiency.

Channel III:

TABLE 3: Price Spread of Milk In Channel III

S. No	Particulars	Price/Ltr.
1	Net price received by producer	45
	Sale price of Producer/ Purchase price of Milk-cooperatives	45
	Cost incurred by the Milk-cooperatives	
	Collection charges	2
	Miscellaneous charges	2
	Margin of Milk-cooperatives	3
	Sale price of Milk-cooperatives/ Purchase price of Processor	52
	Transportation cost	2
	Processing charges	3
	Margin of Processor	2
	Sale price of Processor/Purchase price of retailer	59
	Carriage up to shop	1
	Margin of Retailer	1
	Sale price of retailer/ Purchase price of consumer	61
	Total Marketing cost	9
	Net margin	6
	Price Spread	16
	Marketing efficiency (Conventional Method)	1.77
	Producer's share in consumer rupee	73.77%

Table 4: Marketing Efficiency Of Milk In Different Marketing Channels

Particulars	Units	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
Consumer purchase price	Per Kg	50	55	61
Total marketing price		-	5	9
Total net margin of intermediaries		-	5	6
Marketing efficiency by Conventional method		-	81.81	73.77

Table 4. Marketing efficiency of milk in different channels

Table 4. reveals about the marketing efficiency of different marketing channels in which marketing efficiency of channel II by conventional method is 81.81 and marketing efficiency of channel III is 73.77. The total marketing price was high in channel III in comparison of other channels. The maximum net margin received by market intermediaries is highest in Channel III.

Conclusion

Even the government, co-operative or private institutes should organize training programme before distribution of loans and provide guidance to rural dairy farmers through guidance center or counseling centers through an extension agency. There should be proper marketing channel for the marketing of milk produce. Minimum price of milk should be fixed in the basis of fat content in the milk to encourage the dairy farming among farmers. Proper source of finance should be introduced by government reduce the problem faced by farmers in financing. A standardized methodology for estimating cost of milk production should be followed so that it can be comparable. The estimation of cost and returns from milk production may be initiated as a regular scheme by the Government, wherein the estimates are made as per the standardized methodology at least once in three years. As the daily cost of maintenance does not increase proportionally with the productivity of animals, only way to enhance economic viability of dairy farming is through yield improvement, by disseminating region specific scientific breeding, feeding, health care and management practices. The feed and fodder consumption are not up to the mark which may be one of the reasons for late conceptions

of the animals which require suitable policy measures.

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